

Demand Response Optimization for the Enhancement of the Distribution System's Operation

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Abstract—Following the latest energy market trends, active distribution systems incorporate an ascending mix of flexible loads, which can participate in Demand Response (DR) strategies. The purpose of this research paper is to present a DR strategy for the Distribution System Operator (DSO) in order to enhance the system's operation and mitigate power quality issues, such as voltage drops, and congestion. The proposed algorithm aims at smoothing the load curve, taking into consideration the available flexible load and the limitations of the system. The algorithm is demonstrated on a model of the distribution system of Skiathos island, Greece, in the context of ENFLATE, a Horizon Europe project, and future scenarios with photovoltaic (PV) penetration are studied as well. According to the results, the proposed DR algorithm manages to reduce the voltage drop, eliminate the number of events where the voltage drop exceeds the limits and reduce the losses of the distribution system up to 8%-9%, depending on the PV penetration.

Keywords—demand response, flexibility, distribution system, optimization, power quality, photovoltaic system

I. INTRODUCTION

Demand Response (DR) constitutes one of the contemporary and active strategies adopted by the Distribution System Operators (DSOs) in order to reduce the cost and enhance the efficiency of the system's operation [1]. They are known to be applied in countries such as the Netherlands and the UK, with active participation of the residential sector too, including loads such as heat pumps, washing machines and dishwashers [2]. Furthermore, the ascending market penetration of Electric Vehicles (EVs), which constitute shiftable loads and, therefore, can participate in DR, enhances the value of such strategies. DR can be part of the system's daily operation or may be a useful tool for the operator when the normal operation and the limits of the system are challenged. The latter typically comprises extreme voltage drops, congestion, unbalances, etc., which pose a threat to the power quality or even the stability and seamless operation of the system [3].

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In this context, the authors of [4] present a DR strategy for the mitigation of congestion in transmission systems. Both coal-fired and gas units are considered. The authors focus on cost minimization and the core of the algorithm is a cooperative game pricing method based on Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers (ADMM). In [5] a

market-based Lyapunov optimization framework is proposed to schedule the EV charging and household loads of a distribution system, in order to mitigate congestion issues. The proposed algorithm takes into consideration the DSO as well as the EV aggregator. The authors of [6] present a novel congestion mitigation method based on demand side management. The methodology, which focuses on grid security and user comfort, is based on Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) and takes into consideration the unbalances of the residential network. In [7] a multi-objective particle swarm optimization algorithm for unbalanced distribution systems is presented. The first objective is the minimization of peak load using DR, the second objective is the losses' minimization and the third objective is the unbalance minimization. Assets of the distribution system such as On-Load Tap Changers (OLTC) and capacitors are taken into consideration, as well. The proposed formulation aims to minimize the substation transformer's current unbalance levels. Furthermore, in [8] a simultaneous demand response program and conservation voltage reduction method for optimizing the operation of distribution systems is proposed. The purpose of the optimizer is to reduce the cost of purchasing power, increase the profit from the trade of energy, and improve the reliability of the network.

The purpose of this paper is to highlight the benefits of adopting a DR strategy to optimally schedule flexible loads in a distribution system, in case its normal operation is expected to be challenged for a given, adaptable, time horizon, e.g. within the next twenty four hours. The objective is to provide a smooth load curve, which reduces the losses and voltage drops, thus enhancing the system's operation. Therefore, it expands the purpose of [4], [5], [6], [7], [8] by introducing a new tool to the system operator that focuses on the technical aspects, especially designed to tackle non-normal operation issues. The proposed methodology is tested on a model of the medium voltage distribution network of Skiathos island, Greece, as part of ENFLATE, a Horizon Europe project which tests flexibility solutions in the power sector. Although Skiathos island does not currently have a flexibility market, this study is expected to pave the way towards its successful implementation, which is foreseen in the near future. Furthermore, scenarios with high Photovoltaic (PV) penetration are investigated as Skiathos has high solar potential.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: section II presents the methodology, meaning the mathematical

background of the proposed solution, section III describes the test grid, section IV presents the results, including an analysis for PV penetration and the main conclusions are summarized at the end of the paper.

II. METHODOLOGY

The main concept of the proposed strategy is presented in Fig. 1. More specifically, the power system comprises transformers which may serve regular and flexible load. If the normal operation is expected to have congestion and voltage drop issues, the methodology needs the time series of the regular, non-flexible load to be provided as input. If there is renewable production from Renewable Energy Sources (RES), e.g., PV production, it should be subtracted from the regular load. Then, the overall flexible demand of each transformer for the time interval under study needs to be provided. The input is processed by the optimizer and the result is the decisions for the flexible demand of each transformer at each time step.

Fig. 1. Flow chart of the proposed DR strategy.

Particularly, the core of the methodology is the optimizer's objective function (1), where the decision variables, $d_{n,t}$, are the part of flexible energy demand, E_n^f , of the n -th transformer served at time t , whereas $L_{n,t}^r$ is the regular (non-flexible) power load the n -th transformer at time t . The sum of the transformers' load at each time step is squared. In this way, potential spikes are minimized and the load curve becomes as flat as possible. Consequently, by using this objective function, the algorithm performs peak shaving or valley filling, utilizing the flexible load. The time steps may be hourly but can also have another duration, e.g.,

fifteen minutes or twenty minutes, depending on the resolution required. For the purpose of this study, the optimizer uses hourly time steps.

$$\min F = \sum_t \left(\sum_n \left(d_{n,t} \left(\frac{E_n^f}{\Delta t} \right) + L_{n,t}^r \right) \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

The objective function is subjected to constraints related to the available flexible demand and the technical limitations of the transformers. Constraint (2) ensures that the overall flexible demand of each transformer is served during the examined time interval. Constraint (3) ensures that the decision variables are positive real numbers. Constraint (4) ensures that the load of each transformer at each time step, meaning the sum of flexible and regular load, does not exceed their maximum value, L_n^{\max} .

$$\sum_t d_{n,t} = 1, \forall n \quad (2)$$

$$0 \leq d_{n,t} \leq 1, \forall n, t \quad (3)$$

$$d_{n,t} \left(\frac{E_n^f}{\Delta t} \right) + L_{n,t}^r \leq L_n^{\max}, \forall n, t \quad (4)$$

The optimizer is developed in Pyomo [9]. The solver is Bonmin and utilizes a variety of algorithms including: i) a Non Linear Programming (NLP) based branch-and-bound algorithm, ii) an outer-approximation decomposition algorithm, iii) an implementation of Quesada and Grossmann's branch-and-cut algorithm and iv) a hybrid outer-approximation based branch-and-cut algorithm [10]. The aforementioned algorithms are exact when the objective function and the constraints are convex. Furthermore, the results of Bonmin are cross-verified with other solvers, namely ipopt and couenne, that also specialize in this sort of problems [11], [12]. Ipopt is a software library for large scale nonlinear optimization of continuous systems that implements a primal-dual interior point method and is designed to exploit the first and second derivative. Couenne aims at the optimization of non-convex Mixed Integer NonLinear Programming (MINLP) problems and implements linearization, bound reduction, and branching methods within a branch-and-bound framework.

The effectiveness of the proposed strategy is verified with PowerFactory, DIgSILENT [13]. The results of the optimizer are used as input in a model of the distribution system and the performed power flow analyses showcase how the voltage drops, congestions and losses are expected to be mitigated for the studied time interval.

III. USE CASE ANALYSIS

The proposed strategy is tested on a model of the distribution system of Skiathos island, Greece, presented in Fig. 2. The distribution system operates at 20 kV and was recently interconnected to the mainland through a 150/20 kV substation. Apart from the island's load the 150/20 kV substation also serves other islands, connected to Skiathos. The island, as well as the neighbouring islands, constitute popular tourist destinations, meaning that during summer the load of the substation may rise up to 20 MW. As a general rule for normal operation, the voltage level should not be lower than 0.95 p.u. or higher than 1.05 p.u. and also

not deviate more than 3% from the average voltage level [14].

In the context of ENFLATE project, Horizon Europe, certain residential and commercial loads of the system, installed in several transformers, are considered to participate in flexibility solutions related to congestion management, voltage mitigation, etc. Considering that the flexibility solution is requested for the upcoming twenty four hour horizon, the parameters of the system are presented in Table I. The daily load curve is derived from [15] for medium voltage distribution networks, combining

Fig. 2. Model of the 20 kV distribution system.

* DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM CASE DESCRIPTION

The minimum voltage is equal to 0.942 p.u. and the maximum is equal to 0.985 p.u. Even though the voltage levels are low, the deviation is not higher than 3% from the average. The losses resulted by this operation mode are equal to 4,645 kWh.

In order to prevent the consequences of the aforementioned operation mode, the DSO may implement the proposed DR strategy, the results of which are presented in Fig. 4. It is noted that the flexible loads are scheduled in a manner that relieves the distribution system. In particular, the flexible loads are served mostly during the early hours of the day, instead of the hours when the regular, non-flexible load is served, having a peak of total demand lower than 16 MW. Consequently, the voltage stays higher than 0.95 p.u. at all times, with minimum value equal to 0.952 p.u. The smooth load curve also reduces the losses by 384 kWh, i.e., 8%.

B. Results for PV penetration scenarios

The results before and after the implementation of the proposed algorithm, considering a 1 MW, 5 MW and 10 MW PV installation, as well the results of the current status (without RES) are presented in Table II, which summarizes the total losses of the 20 kV network, and Table III, which summarizes the resulted voltage levels. It should be highlighted that the PV is considered to be installed in the most distant node of the island, where its effect on the system is maximized, and its primary purpose is self-consumption.

The results without and with the implementation of the proposed strategy for 1 MW PV installation are presented in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6, respectively. In this case, the PV production is low, even at its peak. However, it is enough to lift the voltage during noon hours. Therefore, the voltage drops lower than 0.95 p.u. only four times, instead of eight, at 8:00, 18:00, 19:00 and 20:00. The losses are equal to 4,184 kWh, instead of 4,645 kWh, due to self-consumption. Yet, with the implementation of the proposed algorithm, the voltage is higher than 0.95 p.u. at all times and the losses are reduced by 348 kWh, i.e., 8%.

The results for the 5 MW PV system without and with the proposed strategy are presented in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8, respectively. According to Table II, this scenario has the least losses, equal to 3,183 kWh and 2,891 kWh, respectively, i.e., 9% reduction. Without the proposed strategy, the voltage drops below 0.95 p.u. three times, at 18:00, 19:00 and 20:00, when the PV production is low or equal to zero. Moreover, in this scenario the high PV production causes voltage deviation higher than 3% of the average, without DR. However, with DR, both issues are

A. Results for the Current Status of the Distribution System

The operation of the system without the implementation of the proposed algorithm is presented in Fig. 3. It is noted that the depicted active and reactive power values refer to the 150/20 kV substation while the voltage refers to the most distant (and therefore, most affected) 20/0.4 kV transformer of the island. The voltage is lower than 0.95 p.u. for eight hours: in the morning at 8:00 and 9:00, during noon at 11:00, 12:00 and 13:00, and in the evening, at 18:00, 19:00 and 20:00. This is expected, because during these hours the load is high, in this case higher than 16 MW.

Fig. 3. Operation without the proposed algorithm.

Fig. 4. Operation with the proposed algorithm.

Fig. 5.

Fig. 6.

Fig. 7.

Fig. 8.

eliminated because part of the flexible loads are served at noon, when the PV production is maximized.

Finally, the scenario with 10 MW PV showcases the effectiveness of the proposed strategy but also highlights that such an installation would not be beneficial for the system's operation. In more detail, without the implementation of the proposed strategy, the oversized PV system causes higher losses than the 5 MW PV system, equal to 3,668 kWh (which can be reduced by 9% with DR) and also causes high voltage deviations, according to Table III, which can be mitigated with DR but still remain an issue as they are not eliminated. Furthermore, according to Fig. 9 and Fig. 10, the reactive power at the transformer during noon is considerably high, which is a drawback attributed to the fact that the PV system only produces active power. Therefore, such an installation should be coupled with a large storage system.

Summarizing, the effectiveness of the DR strategy is proven in all cases where it is applied, mitigating voltage drops, deviations, load peaks and losses, and a general conclusion about the size of a potential PV installation is drawn.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a simple, yet effective, DR strategy for the mitigation of certain power quality issues that may challenge the normal operation of a distribution system. The purpose of the optimizer is to schedule the flexible demand of each transformer in a way that provides a smooth total load curve with reduced losses and voltage drops or deviations. The strategy is tested on a model of the distribution system of Skiathos island, Greece, in the context of ENFLATE, Horizon Europe. Scenarios

TABLE II. RESULTED LOSSES
TABLE III. RESULTED VOLTAGE

considering PV systems, due to the high solar potential of the island, are studied as well, highlighting its performance, reaching up to 9% losses reduction and elimination of extreme voltage drops and deviations. It is noted that this methodology is suitable for cases where the voltage drop is expected to exceed either the lower or higher limit, as showcased in the results with/without PV penetration. Future work shall include the development of Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) for the forecast of regular and flexible load per 20/0.4 kV transformer and the production of a potential PV system. Furthermore, future work may include the development of the solver in Python, using Lagrange, in order to have an entirely open-source and in-house developed tool.

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